

Structural changes in the judicial system of the Uzbek SSR

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Abstract: Based on the analysis of archival documents and historical sources, this article highlights such provisions as the negative impact of structural changes in the judicial system of the Uzbek SSR from 1930 to 1938, the level of professionalism of judges, ethnic composition, the economically poor state of the courts, insufficient working conditions for full-fledged activity. It also talks about violations in the judicial system and the factors that led to staff turnover.

Keywords: people's court, district court, verdict, decision, collegium, personnel problems.

1. Relevance. Ensuring the true independence of the judiciary, reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, and increasing the level of access to justice are the main priorities of the state policy in the field of reforming the judicial and legal system. In the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, complex measures aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the procedure for selecting and appointing judges, and ensuring that legal, justified and fair court decisions are issued in each case are being implemented. Studying and researching the history of the judicial system, which is an integral part of the history of statehood, is one of the urgent tasks facing the history science.

2. Research methodology. This article is covered on the basis of historical methods - historicity, critical, comparative-logical analysis, sequence, principles of objectivity. The article describes the history of the judicial system during the period when the statute on courts adopted on July 20, 1931 was in effect in the Uzbek SSR.

Formation of the judicial system of the Uzbek SSR researchers of law of the Soviet period X.Suleymanova, A.Rasulev, F.Bakirov. However, the works of these researchers do not mention the contradictions in the process of formation of the Uzbek SSR judicial system, repressions carried out by Soviet authorities, reflecting in one way or another under the influence of the ruling ideology.

During the years of independence, certain aspects of the Soviet judicial system in Uzbekistan were studied by legal researchers. However, in the history of the Uzbekistan, the history of the formation of the judicial system of the Uzbek SSR has not been widely studied as a scientific problem in terms of historical research.

3. Research results. In the 30s of the 20th century, the judicial system of the Uzbek SSR changed several times in accordance with the reforms that took place in the administrative-territorial structure of the republic. In Stalin's article entitled "The Year of the Great Turn", published on November 7, 1929, he justified the "theoretical" aspect of rapid

collectivization[1,P.347]. In order to increase the effectiveness of the policy of violence called collectivization, on July 23, 1930, the USSR Central Committee and the Central Committee of the USSR adopted the decision "On Termination of Districts", which provides for the implementation of a new administrative-territorial division. In particular, the decision stated the following: "... the widespread movement of collectivization in the countryside and the destruction of kulaks as a class, the demand to bring the lower bodies of Soviet power as close as possible to the population in order to ensure the active participation of peasants, poor and middle-class peasants in the socialist reconstruction of the national economy is enough. Bringing the power closer to the population will help to attract the masses of workers and peasants to the practical work of the Soviets" [2, P.676-678].

Clause 1 of the resolution stipulated the complete liquidation of districts by October 1, 1930. In paragraph 14, within twenty days, the leadership of the allied republics was assigned the task of submitting a report to the Presidium of the Ministry of the Interior of the USSR on the measures taken to abolish districts and strengthen the activities of district executive committees.

On August 17, 1930, on the basis of the above decision, the MIQ of the Uzbek SSR made a decision to liquidate the districts. After the termination of the districts, the districts were directly subordinated to the republic. Thus, Uzbekistan was divided into 71 districts, in which 1698 village councils were established.

On December 3, 1930, the Central Executive Committee of the USSR and the Soviet of People's Commissars adopted a decision "On changing the foundations of the judicial system of the USSR and allied republics" [2, P. 1137-1139] in connection with the termination of the districts. Based on the decision, 12 articles of the Law on Courts were amended. In particular, it was stated in the decision that due to the abolition of the district courts, the Supreme Court is the highest instance in relation to the people's courts, and that appeals against the verdicts and decisions of the people's courts will be considered in the Supreme Court in the cassation and control procedure.

At the end of 1930, there were 166 people's courts in Uzbekistan, their number was 147 before the abolition of districts. 49 people's courts operated in cities and 117 in rural areas[3, P.407].

On January 1, 1931, in the joint decree of the People's Commissariat of Justice of the Uzbek SSR and the Supreme Court, an order was given to expand the powers of the people's courts in connection with the abolition of the district courts [4]. In connection with these changes, on July 20, 1931, the Ministry of Justice of the Uzbek SSR adopted the "Regulation on the structure of the judiciary of the Uzbek SSR" of 1926 in a new version [5]. If in the 1926 statute there was a three-level court system in Uzbekistan consisting of the people's court, the district court and the Supreme Court, then a two-level court system consisting of the people's court and the Supreme Court was established based on the new version of the statute.

In accordance with the regulations, people's court precincts were established in each district of the Uzbek SSR. The judge of the People's Court worked alone or together with two people's advisers. A people's judge is elected by the district or city executive committee for a term of one year and approved by the People's Commissariat of Justice. The number of people's court precincts in the district is also determined by the local executive committee.

The list of advisers participating in the People's Court is formed by a special commission formed by local executive committees. Based on the list, 3 people's councilors were summoned to court sessions. 2 of them participated directly in the court sessions, and one of them stood in reserve. In this manner, each people's councilor participated in the court for 10 days during the year. The procedure and conditions for the election of people's councilors were left almost unchanged compared to the previous regulation.

In connection with the abolition of district courts, the powers of the Supreme Court of the Uzbek SSR were expanded accordingly. Including:

- a) providing leadership explanations on the application of laws to all courts of the republic and interpreting the laws of the Uzbek SSR;
- b) canceling or changing the judgments, decisions and rulings of the Supreme Court panels in case they contradict the laws of the entire Union or the Republic;
- c) consideration of cassation appeals and protests against judgments and decisions of people's courts;
- d) consider criminal and civil cases as a court of first instance within the scope of the authority established by law.

The High Court was composed of the Presidium, the Plenum, the commission on criminal cases, the commission on civil cases and the disciplinary commission.

The implementation of zoning in Uzbekistan caused a number of problems in the judicial system, which has not yet been fully formed: firstly, it eliminated the possibility of eliminating cases of law violations committed by people's courts in the territory itself, as it was during the existence of district courts; secondly, it led to an excessive increase in the volume of work in the Supreme Court, which performed the function of the cassation instance in relation to the people's courts; thirdly, at a time when the communication system was not yet well developed, it caused the people who lived in remote districts of the republic to wander for months, waiting for the Supreme Court to positively resolve their complaints about the wrong judgments and decisions of the people's courts.

The above-mentioned problems are especially evident in the southern regions far from the center of the republic and Khorezm. Reorganization of intermediate courts between the Supreme Court and the People's Courts became a vital necessity. Initially, Khorezm district was re-established on April 23, 1932, taking into account the special conditions related to the remoteness of Khorezm [6, P.154]. In this regard, the Khorezm District Court began work based on the decision of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the UZSSR dated July 27, 1933.

The composition of the district court was elected by the district executive committee for a period of one year and approved by the People's Commissariat of Justice of the UzSSR. The composition of Khorezm district court consisted of the Presidium, Plenum, and commissions for criminal and civil cases. The powers of the District Court Presidium, Plenary, and Panels were virtually unchanged from the 1926 statute.

The district court had jurisdiction to:

- A) supervising the activities of the people's courts as the central court office in the district;
- B) consideration of appeals and protests against judgments and decisions of people's courts as a cassation instance;
- C) considering criminal and civil cases that are not within the jurisdiction of the people's courts as a court of first instance.

Later, Kashkadarya and Surkhondarya districts were reorganized based on the decision of the Central Committee of the USSR on February 23, 1935. District courts also functioned in these districts[3, P.628].

By 1935, the UzSSR administratively consisted of 3 districts and 94 districts. People's courts operating on the territory of Uzbekistan can be divided into the following 4 groups:

- A) 164 people's courts located in the districts directly subordinated to the republic;

- B) 14 people's courts located in Khorezm district;
- C) 17 people's courts located in the territory of Kashkadarya district;
- D) 13 people's courts located in Surkhandarya district [7].

Complaints regarding verdicts and decisions of the people's courts operating in the districts under the republic were considered in the Supreme Court of the UzSSR in the cassation procedure. In relation to the people's courts located in Khorezm, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya districts, the respective district courts performed the function of cassation instance. Thus, in 1935, in the judicial system of the UzSSR, the courts of general jurisdiction consisted of the following: 1) people's court; 2) district court; 3) Supreme Court of the Uzbek SSR.

In 1935, the Supreme Court of the UzSSR as a court of first instance received 410 cases, of which 395 were considered, and the remaining 15 were left for the next year [8].

One of the most serious and unsolved problems in the People's Courts was the issue of personnel. Most of the judges did not have specialized knowledge and professional training. These opinions are confirmed by the information recorded in the archive documents. For example, on July 27, 1936, Saidali Khojaev, People's Commissar of Justice of the UzSSR, submitted a report on the results of the inspection of people's courts to N.V. Krylenko, People's Commissar of Justice of the UzSSR. According to him, 35 percent of the people's judges in the Uzbek SSR reported that they were released from their positions because they did not have enough knowledge and skills and regularly violated the law. In particular, according to the results of the audit, 66 people's judges were sent to study for retraining, 61 were released from their positions, and 14 were transferred to lower positions [9].

The level of professional training of people's judges can be learned from the annulled judgments and decisions. For example, during 1936, 1,660 criminal cases and 2,715 civil cases tried by the people's courts were considered and canceled by the higher courts in the cassation and control procedure.

In 1937, 209 people's courts were registered in the Uzbek SSR, but 201 of them were functioning, and the remaining 8 were not functioning due to lack of specialists.

The level of knowledge of the existing 201 people's court judges in Uzbekistan in the legal field was as follows: 10 had a higher education, 15 had an elementary education, 74 had completed a three-month training course for lawyers, and 102 had no education [10]. Judging from the above figures, more than half of the judges of the people's court in Uzbekistan did not even have basic education.

People's Commissar of Justice S. Khojaev spoke about 10 highly educated judges of the people's court and noted that although they graduated from the Institute of Soviet Law and Construction in Tashkent in 1936, they did not have practical experience in the field.

The national composition of the judges of the People's Court was very diverse. At this point, it should be noted that Uzbeks made up a large part of the judges. For example, out of 201 people's court judges, 123 were Uzbek, 32 Russian, 15 Kazakh, 10 Jewish, 9 Tatar, 4 Bashkir, 4 Tajik, 2 Turkmen, 1 Uyghur, 1 Chuvash [11].

The shortage of experts in the field of judicial law was a situation not only in Uzbekistan, but also in all the republics of the former Soviet Union. For example, the following information was published in one of the central publications of the Soviet judiciary: "At the moment, the legal training of the current composition of judges is at an extremely low level. As of January 1, 1937, 2,202 out of 4,616 judges in the RSFSR did not have a higher education, or even legal courses. The situation is similar in other allied republics. 206 out of 311 judges in Belarus, 170

out of 239 judges in Georgia, 305 out of 490 judges in Uzbekistan, 735 out of 1264 judges in Ukraine do not have legal education" [12, P.10-11]. When information is given about 490 judges in Uzbekistan, the entire judicial system, in particular the judges of military tribunals and line courts, is also included.

In a number of districts of the Uzbek SSR, people's courts were not provided with sufficient buildings, inventories, codes and other necessary regulatory and legal documents for their operation. Most of the buildings allocated for the People's Courts were in a state of disrepair, and the government had not allocated sufficient funds to repair them. For example, in 1937, the People's Commissar of Justice S. Khojaev asked the government to allocate funds from the budget for the construction of 15 people's courts[13]. However, the government refused to this reasonable request. People's courts in Kashkadarya stated that there was a shortage of paper for proceedings, and a lack of Criminal and Civil Codes[14].

In 1936, the territory of the Karakalpakstan ASSR was removed from the RSFSR and included in the UzSSR. This situation was formalized in the Constitution of the UzSSR adopted in 1937.

In 1938, an administrative-territorial division was implemented in the UzSSR in order to quickly guide the development of the national economy. On January 15, 1938, districts were abolished in Uzbekistan for the second time, and Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Fergana and Khorezm regions were established on the territory of the republic. In connection with the formation of regions, regional courts started working in these regions. As a result, the courts of general jurisdiction in the judicial system of the Uzbek SSR became the following: 1) People's Court, 2) Regional Court, 3) Supreme Court of the Karakalpakstan SSR, 4) Supreme Court of the Uzbek SSR.

As of July 1, 1938, there were 221 precincts of people's courts in the Uzbek SSR. In practice, only 196 of them worked, and the remaining 25 were declared vacant due to the lack of specialists. 11 judges of the people's court in Uzbekistan had higher education, 37 had secondary education, and 148 had primary education[15].

The Stalinist repression of 1937-1938, as in other areas, caused some of the judges of the People's Court to be unjustly accused and punished. In particular, in 1938, 6 people's judges were imprisoned as enemies of the people, and 53 others were released from their positions.

The situation in the regional courts was also not satisfactory. 14 people worked in the Tashkent regional court, while 21 employees were supposed to work by state. A similar situation prevailed in other regions. In particular, 13 judges worked in Bukhara region, 12 in Samarkand region, 12 in Ferghana, and 7 in Khorezm. 11 of the regional court judges in the entire republic had higher education, 18 had secondary education, and 34 had primary education[16].

The Supreme Court of the Uzbek SSR employed 25 employees statewide. Of these, 7 had higher education, 9 had secondary education and 9 had Primary Education[17].

This system was in effect until the adoption of the law "On the structure of the judiciary of the USSR and allied republics" on August 16, 1938.

4. Conclusion. In conclusion, when studying the activity of the judicial system of the Uzbekistan SSR between 1930 and 1938, it was found that despite some structural changes in the field, there were no positive changes. Firstly, the implementation of changes in the administrative-territorial structure without a good study of existing internal opportunities and conditions caused instability and anarchy in the judicial system. Secondly, in the 30s of the 20th century, the personnel problem did not find its solution. Not only in people's courts, but also in district and regional courts, most of the judges remained unqualified. Thirdly, the election of the judges of the people's court, the district court, and later the regional court for a period of one year and the replacement of judges every year harms the authority and reputation

of the courts of general jurisdiction. In addition, the election of judges by local executive committees, rather than by the central government agencies, created dependence on these agencies. Fourthly, as a result of the implementation of Stalinist repressions in the 1930s, attention was paid to the OGPU, NKVD, "special troika", "special two" agencies, which were given emergency judicial powers by the authoritarian Soviet government, and the courts of general jurisdiction were limited in all respects. Even industry representatives were repressed. Fifth, the courts were not well financed. Judges were not paid on time and did not have the necessary inventory for proceedings.

So, in a word, the people's courts and the judges in the system could not become the defenders of the people's interests. Courts of general jurisdiction remained unsupplied, as in the 20s of the 20th century, and most of their employees remained legally ignorant.

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